
MONEY SUPPLY AND INFLATION NEXUS IN NIGERIA: THE ROLE OF EXPECTATIONS AND FISCAL OPERATIONS

DR. (MRS.) CHIKANELE ASURU

**Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State
Email: chikasu4favour@gmail.com**

Abstract

Here, the inspiration of ‘money supply on inflation in Nigeria’ was studied by making reference to the sway of expectations and fiscal operations of the government. The paper put to use data that considered thirty-five (35) years data point ranging from 1986 through 2020. The study utilized the ‘autoregressive distributed lag’ (ARDL) technique and ‘Granger Causality’ test in analysing the data. Given the ARDL result, we observed that expectation has a substantial sway on the present inflation. Further, the F-Bounds test result reported that cointegration exist, leading to the estimation of the short-run dynamic ‘error correction model’ and the long run estimates. In the short-run, it was observed that changes in money supply wielded no significant influence on the variations in the rate of inflation; while output growth and fiscal depth wielded a negative and significant sway. In the long-run, it was discovered that broad money supply wielded a positive and substantial influence while output growth put forth a negative and significant effect. The fiscal depth of the government was observed to wield a positive though an insignificant long-run influence on the rate of inflation. The result from the Granger causality test supported that growth in money supply causes inflation. It follows from the findings that for inflation to be tackled successfully, there is need to maintain a stable level of money supply along with maintaining a substantial growth in output, while maintaining the fiscal depth within the 25% as suggested in the critical limit hypothesis.

Keywords: Critical Limit Hypothesis, Adaptive Expectation, Rational Expectation, Inflation, Fiscal Depth.

1 Introduction

The persistent rise in the price level of commodities is what has been generally accepted to be described as inflation. With different choice of words though linking up to the same idea, scholars have attempted to proffer different definitions to the issue of inflation. Inflation, in the view of Pigou (1947), is the continuous or ongoing tendency for the price level to surge. Therefore, a

consistent and noticeable rise in the overall level of prices can also be referred to as inflation. Amadeo (2012) described it as “when the prices of the majority of products and services continue to creep upward”, resulting in a fall in the quality of living. The hint that inflation is a monetary phenomenon, making monetary policy mainly responsible for its abatement has come to be the most recognized view.

In line with the above line of thinking, which is centred on the “quantity theory” of money, the only factor affecting inflation is the change in the relative supply of commodities and money (Ofori, Danquah and Zhang, 2017). To Christiano and Fitzgerald (2003), when the rate of inflation is gentle enough, households and firms do not need to consider price variations while making daily decisions. Each piece of money buys less commodities when the overall price level surges. So, inflation indicates a diminution in buying power per the piece of money, or a loss of real value in the economy's medium of exchange and unit of account (Ofori *et al.*, 2017).

The argument behind the “quantity theory” as summarized in the “equation of exchange” is that the price level, P , is proportional to the changes in the quantity of money, M , given that the velocity (V) is constant along with the total output (Y or T in the case of transaction). The implication here is that if money supply intensifies, the price level will respond in a similar manner. This comes to be the monetarist view of inflation. Apart from money supply being attributed to be the driving force of inflation, the Keynesian economists have brought up the argument that if aggregate demand falls short of aggregate supply, the economy will likely experience an inflationary gap which can be corrected via a contractionary fiscal measures of reducing the government spending or increasing taxation plus a combination of both measures if desirable. These two views therefore point to the fact that inflationary pressures in the economy needs both monetary and fiscal measures to be tackled.

To present a threshold for the government spending level in the economy that will not intensify inflation in the economy, a threshold of 25% of the overall economic activity is expected to be maintained by the government while deciding on her expenditure decisions. This came to be known as the “critical limit hypothesis” which was put forth by Collin Clerk. As such, even if the government maintains a balanced budget and spend beyond this critical limit, inflation will occur (Atan and Effiong, 2021). This points to the fact that the fiscal depth of the government is of immense importance in ensuring price stability in the domestic economy. In the case of Nigeria, this limit has not been

reached as the fiscal depth of the government was 0.10% in 1986 but grew steadily up to 14.52% in 2020. In line with this hypothesis, the rising trend poses an impending inflationary pressures if the 25% level is reached and exceeded. This rising trend is an outcome of the high fiscal deficit that is being maintained by the government in recent times.

The use of monetary and fiscal policy stance in combating inflation has been a complicated issue in deriving the desired level of inflation. Apart from money supply and government revenue and expenditure tools, inflation is also being influenced by structural issues like market anomalies, structural rigidities, social tension, foreign exchange, political instability, inelasticity of food supply, and decline in export earnings (Ezirim, *et al.*, 2012). These aforementioned issues cannot be duly tackled with monetary and fiscal policies, and they create a mismatch between demand and supply thereby intensifying the inflationary pressures in the economy.

Inflation is being noted as one of the chief defies confronting emerging countries, including Nigeria, that must be addressed (Ojalere, 2019). For years, the inflationary strain has risen, having a deleterious sway on the Nigerian economy through the amplification of commodity prices. Against this backdrop, Nigeria's monetary authority has implemented a variety of monetary policy tools with the primary goal of keeping inflation under control. Despite this, inflation in Nigeria has been steadily rising in the considered era.

The rate of inflation, money supply growth, and fiscal depth of the government has been exhibiting some changes over the years. Table 1 captures the value of these variables for some chosen years.

Table 1: Inflation, money supply growth, and fiscal depth in Nigeria for selected years

Year	Inflation (%)	Growth Rate of Broad Money Supply (%)	Fiscal Depth (%)
1986	13.70	4.23	0.10
1990	3.60	45.92	0.28
1995	51.60	19.41	1.15
2000	14.50	48.07	2.79
2005	11.60	24.35	5.00
2010	11.80	6.91	7.68
2015	9.60	6.06	7.23
2019	11.98	9.16	13.61
2020	15.75	30.57	14.52

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, 2020.

The rate of inflation as at 1986 was 13.70% given the money supply growth rate of 4.23% and fiscal depth of 0.10%. As the money supply grew by 45.92% in 1990 with a fiscal depth of 0.28%, a tremendous increase in inflation from 3.60% in 1990 to 51.60% in 1995 was recorded. To curtail this, the monetary authority reduced the supply of money as indicated by the growth rate of 19.41% in 1995, leading the price level to decline to 14.50%. Over the years, the fiscal depth of the government has been rising steadily but what is common is that it has not reached the critical limit of 25% set by Colin Clerk. We cannot therefore say that fiscal depth has been inflationary. Meanwhile, changes in money supply could be said to be a driver of the changes in the rate of inflation as it seems to portray some similar movement over the years. Figure 1 captures these movements where both the growth in money supply and inflation exhibited high degree of volatility.

Figure 1: Trend in money supply growth and inflation in Nigeria, 1986 – 2020

With the growing volatility in the growth rate of money supply in the 1980s and early 1990s, it is observed that the rate of inflation was also largely volatile as it portrays series of oscillations within that time. This similar behaviour replicated on the opposite direction in the late 1990s and 2000s where despite the volatility in money supply, the rate of inflation has been a bit stable. The statistic of 2019 and 2020 are of concern as they portrayed a rising money supply growth from 9.16% to 30.57% respectively; followed by a rising inflation from 11.98% in 2019 to 15.75% in 2020.

Given this behaviour, could it be that rising money supply growth could intensify the rate of inflation in Nigeria as projected by the quantity theory of money? This forms the basis in which this paper seeks to study the influence of

money supply growth on inflation in Nigeria from 1986 via 2020 with special consideration of expectations and fiscal depth of the government. The paper also aims at examining the pattern of the causal relationship concerning the rate of inflation and the growth rate of money supply in Nigeria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The theoretical literature that are of relevance to this study are the quantity theory of money, demand-pull and cost-push theories of inflation, structuralist theory of inflation, expectation theory, and the critical limit hypothesis. The summary of these theories are given as follows:

2.1.1 The Quantity Theory of Money

The ‘quantity theory of money’ (QTM) entails the monetarist view of inflation as encapsulated by Friedman (1989). Based on the theory, “inflation is nothing but the pecuniary incident which is emerged by the monetary expansion” (Sultana *et al.*, 2018). The QTM with Milton Friedman leading holds that inflation is every time and universally a monetary incident that stem from from a speedy increase in the quantity of money than in total output (Friedman, 1989). Thus, it presupposes a direct proportional link concerning money supply and the price level. Using the “Fisher Equation of Exchange” (FEX), the theory bases its argument.

The FEX is demonstrated using the equations below:

$$MV = PY \quad (2.1)$$

In which M = money supply, V = velocity of circulation of money (the number of times which money changes in hand), P = price level, and Y = level of output. With the assumption that V and Y are constant, then P varies with M in a proportional manner and M does not affect Y as stipulated in the neutrality of money argument (Ebipre and Amaegberi, 2020).

It therefore follows from the above argument that,

$$P = f(M) \quad (2.2)$$

Indicating that the price level (inflation), P, changes in proportionality with the volume of money supply, M, in circulation. The QTM therefore relates a rise in money supply with attendant decline in the value of money, implying that growth in money supply cause inflation. This made the monetarists to believe that “only money matters”, consequently monetary policy is more powerful in economic stabilization compared to fiscal Policy (Ebipre and Amaegberi, 2020). As Ebipre and Amaegberi (2020) puts, the monetarists view money

supply as the “dominate, though not exclusive” determinant of both the level of output and prices.

2.1.2 Demand-Pull Theory of Inflation

Keynes (1936) is of the opinion that demand-pull inflation is an aftermath of an upturn in aggregate demand which comprises investment, consumption, and government spending. This kind of inflation emerges when aggregate demand fall short of aggregate supply, thereby creating an inflationary gap in the economy. As enunciated by Ebipre and Amaegberi (2020), the more the gap between aggregate demand and aggregate supply, the more will be the rise in the rate of inflation. The demand intensifying factors include government expenditure, exports, taxation, debt repayment, private expenditures, and shortage of goods (Joshi, 2021). This hue of inflation is attributed to the Keynesian economists and they portray that aggregate demand-inhibiting factors such as reduction in government spending, tax increase and money supply control individually or collectively can be effective in curtailing effective demand and then controlling inflation.

2.1.3 Cost-Push Theory of Inflation

The cost-push inflation emanates from factors like increase in wages, increase in profit margin, international reasons, war, natural calamities, hoarding, and scarcity of inputs for production (Joshi, 2021), and entails a socio-political interpretation (Alpanda *et al.*, 2010). This view of inflation is attributed to a couple of non-monetary supply shock factors which are foreseeable to escalate costs and consequently the prices in the economy (Ebipre and Amaegberi, 2020).

2.1.4 Structuralist Theory of Inflation

This theory relates inflation as an outcome of market imperfections and structural imbalances prevalent in some sectors of developing economies, which creates the mismatch between the demand and supply thereby leading to rising inflation (Sultana *et al.*, 2018). Other structural factors as put forth by Ezirim, *et al.* (2012) include “social tension, decline in export earnings, rise in demand for food, relative inelasticity of food supply, industrialization, foreign exchange, and political instabilities” (Ebipre and Amaegberi, 2020). In this light, the structuralist theory of inflation portrays that the aforementioned issues cannot be rectified via monetary and fiscal actions.

2.1.5 The Theory of Expectations

Clark and Davig (2009) has earlier opined that expectations are an essential force in inflation dynamics. To this, shocks in long-term inflationary expectations are keen to propel tenacious rise in inflation; while shocks to the short-term expectations are viewed to be highly transitory. The inflation expectations react to an array of variables, mainly past inflation (adaptive expectation), plus the situation of the economy along with monetary and fiscal policy actions.

Going by adaptive expectation where expectation is based on the past inflation, the model can be expressed as:

$$P_e = \beta P_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2.3)$$

Where P_e is next year's inflation that is being currently expected, P_{t-1} is the current year's inflation that was expected the previous year, β captures the slope coefficient, and ε_t is the error term which is stochastic. If $\beta = 1$, then next year's inflation will simply be the same as the current year's inflation and this is in line with the prediction of the adaptive expectation hypothesis.

Meanwhile, inflation expectation can also be rational where the economic agent incorporates all available information in forecasting the rate of inflation. In this case, the expected rate of inflation is achieved not only through the use of the past value, but by monitoring the policy stance of the government at both the monetary and fiscal level. It is worthy of note that the potency of such policy actions will depend on whether they are anticipated or unanticipated. In forming expectations, allowing for an explicit time variation in long-term is of great importance (Bernanke, 2007).

Assuming that the current rate of inflation, P_t , can be influenced by an exogenous shock, it can be expressed as:

$$P_t = P^* + \sigma_1 P_{t+1e} - P^* + \sigma_2 U_{pt} + \sigma_3 U_{yt} \quad (2.4)$$

P_{t+1e} is the expected inflation, P^* is the target inflation, U_p is the price shock, U_y is the demand shock, σ_1 to σ_3 are the parameters. It follows from Equation (2.4) that present inflation deviates from its target in part to the deviancy of expected inflation from the target (Bonatti et al., 2022). Given this, the core issue could be on how to form the expectation. This steers to the issue of anchored expectation and unanchored expectation.

In anchored expectation, the expectation is formed using target inflation and are unresponsive to transitory shocks. Thus by assuming that $P_{t+1e} = P^*$,

$$P_t = P^* + \sigma_2 U_{pt} + \sigma_3 U_{yt} \quad (2.5)$$

Due to the aftermaths of the shocks, Equation (2.5) portrays that the current rate of inflation drifts around its targets.

For the unanchored expectation, “they are not kept in line the central bank's target, the reason being that they result to be sensitive to shocks, or better to the consequent evolution of the actual inflation” (Bonatti et al., 2022). The starting point for this is derived from the rational expectations (RE). The RE of inflation is derived by taking the expected value of the evolution of actual inflation given in Equation (2.4) as $E(P_{t-1})$,

$$P^e_{t+1} = EP_{t+1} = P^* + \sigma_1(E(P_{t+1}) - P^*) + \sigma_2(E(U_{pt+1}) + \sigma_3(E(U_{yt+1})) - - (2.6)$$

There are two key insinuations from Equation (2.6): (i) RE demands understanding of the statistical link of future values of U_p and U_y with their current values; (ii) RE do maintain the likelihood of being self-fulfilling, nevertheless they also have the necessary attribute that they calibrate themselves with actual inflation and the inflation target if the central bank check inflation appropriately (Bonatti et al., 2022). This is observable under one of the utmost general hypotheses about shocks – that U_p and U_y chart a random walk, suggesting that they enclose no facts about their future values. Consequently, $E(u_{pt+1})(E(U_{yt+1}))=0$ Then the result of Equation (2.6) requires that $E(p_{t+1})=P^*$ returning to Equation (2.4) of ‘anchored expectations’.

2.1.6 Critical Limit Hypothesis

Using inter-war data of numerous Western countries, Collin Clerk put forth the “Critical Limit Hypothesis” as a macro model of public expenditure. As portrayed in the hypothesis, inflation will occur even under a balanced budget if the share of the government sector goes beyond 25% of aggregate economic activities. When it exceeds 25%, the implication will be that income earners will face reduced incentives to work because of the implied high incidence of tax, causing their productivity to plunge. Due to the declining productivity by the income earners, the resultant effect will be that aggregate output will also plummet. Since exceeding the 25% implies more government spending, the effect of such spending will be that the intensity of demand will be aggravated. This pushes up prices even at a balanced budget. The implication of this is that if a nation desires to keep inflation at the least possible level, the 25% limit must be observed. This hypothesis therefore captures the effect of fiscal depth on inflation within an economy.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Scholars have delved into diverse studies on the money supply, expectations, fiscal policy actions, and inflation in different countries and using different approaches and time frame. A study by Clark and Davig (2009) was geared towards establishing empirical evidence concerning inflation and expectation. Their observation was that “expectations are driving force in inflation

dynamics, with long-run expectations, which are indistinguishable to trend inflation, highly central than short-run expectations”. Inflation expectations react to a wide array of variables, largely past inflation, but also to the economic circumstance cum monetary policy stance.

Sola and Peter (2013) used data from 1970 through 2008 to study the money supply and inflation connection for Nigeria by putting the OLS and VAR approaches to use. The causality test results reported indication of a one-way causality gushing from money supply to inflation; while the OLS result supported a positive influence of money supply on inflation, where such an effect was also seen to be significant. The causality test indicated a one-way causality flowing from money supply to inflation, making the paper to recommend the need to use inflation as a guide towards measuring the potency of monetary policy in the economy.

The study of Sabade (2014) for India was to check the cogency of the QTM and to provide an alternative postulation on the rapport concerning money supply and inflation. The study reported that the $MV = PT$ identity is true. However, the functional rapport concerning M and P expressed as $P = f(M)$ does not hold in respect to the Indian economy due to constancy assumption of V and T. To check inflation in the Indian economy, the study recommended that agricultural productivity should be boosted along with warehousing and supply-chain management.

At the fiscal policy realm as it affects inflation, Otto and Ukpere (2015) used Nigeria data spanning from 1989 through 2011. By making use of the OLS cointegration and Granger causality approach, the result indicated that government spending do not wield any substantial inspiration on the rate of inflation. While the cointegration test supported evidence of long-run effect of fiscal policy and inflation; the Granger causality test upheld a bidirectional causality concerning the two variables.

Tule et al. (2015) examined the money/inflation dynamics in Nigeria as it affects the accomplishment of monetary policy stance from the first quarter of 1982 to the fourth quarter of 2012. The technique follows the VAR and different variants of the OLS – ordinary least squares, fully modified, and dynamic OLS. The effect of money supply on inflation was reported to be positive and momentous in the diverse variants of OLS, pointing that money supply and inflation has a long-run connection. By splitting the data point two – 1982Q1 to 1996Q4 and 1996Q1 to 2012Q4, the money supply coefficient

remained significant in 1982Q1 to 1996Q4 but became insignificant for 1996Q1 to 2012Q4 thus pointing out the weakening money/inflation association in recent times.

Still in Nigeria, Egbulonu and Wobilor (2016) used data from 1970 through 2013 to analyse the link concerning fiscal policy and inflation; with OLS, cointegration and error correction mechanism serving as the analysis technique. While a long-run equilibrium relationship was reported concerning the two variables, a positive effect of government expenditure and tax on inflation which was also insignificant was recorded.

For the era 1967 through 2015, Ofori et al. (2017) studied the sway of money supply on Ghana's inflation making use of the OLS estimation method. The outcome is of the support that a long-run link exist concerning money supply and inflation, which is positive and noteworthy.

In the study by Sultana et al. (2018) for Bangladesh, the cointegration and VECM approach were applied to monthly data from March 2010 through December 2017 to discover the rapport concerning money supply and inflation. The result revealed that money supply failed to wield any short-run weight on inflation but a two-way directional causality concerning the two variables were established in the long-term.

Olalere (2019) in the quest to study the money supply and inflation rapport in Nigeria made use of data from 1980 through 2009. With the aid of the VECM, the study unveils that the long-run rapport concerning inflation and money supply is a positive one, which is also significant. The adoption of policy measures that could plummet the volume of money in circulation in the country by the monetary authority was the chief recommendation of the study.

Ebipre and Amaegberi (2020) took their turn to the Nigeria case by studying the liaison concerning money supply and inflation from 1971 through 2015 with the use of the OLS approach which the study reported to be inappropriate. Result pointed out that the both money supply and deficit financing put forth a positive weight on inflation in Nigeria. Further findings x-ray the importance of productivity growth in reducing inflation in the long-run.

Sanusi (2020) strived at estimating the extent of fiscal supremacy in Nigeria along with South Africa by examining extent of fiscal cum monetary policies complementarity. The outcome pointed out that the extent of fiscal supremacy

was 0.16 and 0.33 for Nigeria and South Africa respectively derived from the fiscal and monetary policy interdependence coefficient of 0.84 and 0.67, indicating lower level of fiscal supremacy though that of South Africa is greater than Nigeria. This implies that CBN has larger autonomy to combat inflation. Yet, the Nigeria still records higher inflation likened to South Africa, making the study to conclude that the two countries should endeavour more to sustain the current level of their autonomy given their higher degree of fiscal and monetary policies interdependence.

Okon et al. (2021) inquired into whether the problem of inflation is unsolvable in the Nigerian case. By putting to use data from 1970 through 2018 which were analysed using the OLS approach and Granger causality test, it was captured that government expenditure, money supply, and interest rate put forth positive effects on inflation, with the effects being significant.

In Nepal, Joshi (2021) was recently concerned with establishing the short-run cum long-run link concerning inflation and money supply for 1964/1965 through 2018/2019 based on the ARDL bounds test for cointegration. Result from the analysis portrayed existence of cointegration and the error correction term was reported to be involved in correcting about 98% of the overall discrepancies in the short-run to establish a long-run equilibrium in the model.

Atan and Effiong (2021) took their turn to test the validity if the critical limit hypothesis by studying the influence of fiscal policy on inflation in Nigeria. The study engage data from 1991 through 2019 which was analysed exploiting the ARDL approach. In the long-run and short-run estimates, it was observed that government activities (fiscal depth) do not wield any significant influence on inflation since the economy has not yet reached the 25% critical limit.

3 Methodology

3.1 The Model

Given the goal of detecting the inspiration of money supply on inflation in the midst of expectation and fiscal depth, our model is specified by modifying that of Atan and Effiong (2021) and is specified thus;

$$INF_t = f(INF_{t-1}, MSS_t, GDP_t, GXGD_t, IMP_t) \quad (3.1)$$

Where INF_t is the current rate of inflation, INF_{t-1} is the previous year's rate of inflation which measures expectation, MSS is the growth rate of broad money supply, GDP_t is output growth, $GXGD_t$ is the ratio of total government expenditure to GDP which measures fiscal depth of the government, and

IMP_t is the import volume index.

By transforming Equation (3.1), an econometric form is obtained below which is amendable to estimation.

$$INF_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 INF_{t-1} + \gamma_2 MSS_t + \gamma_3 GDP_t + \gamma_4 GXGD_t + \gamma_5 IMP_t + \mu_t \quad (3.2)$$

It is clear that our specified econometric model includes the constant, γ_0 , which portrays that we are operation a regression model which is not through the origin; the parameters to be estimated are captured by γ_0 , to γ_5 ; while is the error term. Given the parameters, it is expected that γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_5 , γ_2 should be positive; while γ_3 and γ_4 , should be negative.

3.2 Measurement of Variables

The rate of inflation is measured in percentages as the annual changes in the consumer prices, which reflects the changes in the price level of goods and services in the economy. The growth rate in broad money supply is also measured in percentages to capture the changes in the money supply in the economy. Such changes gives are based on the monetary policy stance of the monetary authority and gives signal on what will happen to the price level. GDP is measured in percentages as the annual growth in the gross domestic product of the country which is an indicator of economic growth. GXGD is measured in percentages as the ratio of total government expenditure to GDP, and measures the financial depth of the government in the economy. Lastly, IMP is the import volume index where 2,000 = 100. This index gives us the intensity of importation in the country and could be a key driver of foreign exchange pressure which could have a substantial weigh on domestic prices.

3.3 Nature Sources of Data

For this study, data spanning from 1986 to 2020 are utilized which reflect a period of thirty-five (35) years. The duration so selected is long enough to capture some dynamics in the economic variable of interest, along with changes in money supply and fiscal depth of the government. The Central Bank of Nigeria, CBN, (2021) annual statistical bulletin and the World Bank (2021) publication on “World Development Indicators” served as the sources of our data. For the CBN, the variables so obtained from include the rate of inflation, growth rate of broad money supply, output growth, and fiscal depth; while import volume index was gotten from the World Bank database.

3.4 Technique of Analysis

The study is conducted using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method. This method is selected based on the time series properties of our

variables. Also, we utilized the Granger Causality test to detect the direction of the rapport between money supply and inflation.

3.4.1 Unit Root Test

To define the time series properties of our variables, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity of the variables is being put to use. The test equation follows the constant and trend assumption as is specified as follows:

$$\Delta R_t = \phi + \theta t + \beta_1 R_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i R_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.3)$$

In Equation (3.3), R is the time series variable to be tested for unit root; ϕ is the constant and θt captures the trend component; the summation aspect reflects the augmented aspect of the model to correct for serial correlation; R_{t-1} captures the previous value of R; i is the number of lag which is selected automatically by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC); ε_t is the error term; β_1 and is the coefficient to be tested for unit root. For the test, the ‘null hypothesis’ is that R contains a unit root expressed as $\beta_1 = 1$. The test is accomplished at the 5% level where it is expected that the ADF statistic must be more negative than the 5% critical value before the ‘null hypothesis’ is overruled.

3.4.2 Bounds Test for Cointegration

The use of the ARDL approach facilitates the use of the F-Bounds test for levels relationship. The test aids in detecting if the variables in the model exhibits any long-run relationship given that they are not all integrated of order one. The test is conducted at the 1% level where it is expected that for cointegration to exist, the F-statistic must lie within the I(0) and I(1) critical bounds values.

3.4.3 Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model

Since our analysis is based on the ARDL approach, the model is specified thus;

$$INF_t = \delta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_1 INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_2 MSS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^r \delta_3 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^s \delta_4 GXGD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \delta_5 IMP_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3.4$$

If there is cointegration, the ARDL model is transformed into a short-run error correction model which is expressed as follows.

$$\Delta INF_t = \delta_0 + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_1 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \delta_2 \Delta MSS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^r \delta_3 \Delta GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^s \delta_4 \Delta GXGD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \delta_5 \Delta IMP_{t-i} + \varphi ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3.5$$

Where φ is the error correction mechanism which must be negative and statistically significant before the model can adjust to long-run equilibrium. The

use of the ARDL short-run error correction model helps us in estimable robust short-run dynamic coefficients along with the long-run estimates at the same time.

3.4.4 Granger Causality Test

In detecting the nature of the causal bond concerning money supply and inflation, the Granger causality test is conducted and the test equation is specified thus ;

$$INF_t = \theta + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i INF_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \delta_j MSS_{t-i} + \epsilon_{1t} \quad 3.6$$

And

$$MSS_t = \theta + \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi_i MSS_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_j INF_{t-i} + \epsilon_{2t} \quad 3.7$$

For Equation (3.6), it is stated that the current value of INF depends on its past values and the past values of MSS; while Equation (3.7) stipulates that the current value of MSS depends on its past values and that on the past values of INF. The coefficients δ_j and γ_j are the respective measures of the influence of MSS_{t-i} on INF_t and the influence of INF_{t-i} on MSS_t . In this way, the ‘null hypothesis’ is stated that Granger causality does not occur: $\delta_j = 0$ and $\gamma_j = 0$. The embracing of the ‘null hypothesis’ implies that the variables do not Granger cause each other. Yet, there are two other scenarios that may occur – unidirectional causality where either δ_j or γ_j is significant, and bidirectional causality where both δ_j and γ_j are significant. The test is conducted using the F-statistic.

4 EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive properties of our times series variables are computed and Table 2 reflects on the result.

Table 2: Descriptive properties of the variables

	INF	MSS	IMP	GDP	GXGD
Mean	19.8438	23.4092	204.0690	4.5792	4.6921
Median	12.0000	21.5500	136.3289	4.2059	3.9540
Maximum	76.7589	57.7816	437.5121	14.6044	14.5178
Minimum	0.2236	-2.0100	62.8618	-1.9200	0.0954
Std. Dev.	18.4351	15.9947	127.2274	3.8982	3.9738
Skewness	1.7584	0.4482	0.4686	0.4459	0.6735

Kurtosis	4.9421	2.3050	1.6392	2.7289	2.7192
Jarque-Bera	23.5365	1.8764	3.9817	1.2671	2.7611
(Probability)	(0.0000)***	(0.3913)	(0.1366)	(0.5307)	(0.2514)
Observations	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

Over the thirty-five (35) years data points reflected in this study, it is observed that the mean of inflation (INF) is 19.84% which is clearly on the double digit. With the standard deviation of 18.44%, the variable has a coefficient of variation amounting to 92.94% which is quite wide. For growth rate of broad money supply (MSS), it is reported that the variable averaged 23.41% with a standard deviation of 15.99% thus giving a 68.30% coefficient of variation. Import volume index (IMP) is characterised by a 204.07 mean value and a standard deviation of 127.23 giving rise to a 62.35% coefficient of variation. To output growth (GDP), the variable has a mean of 4.58% and a standard deviation of 3.90%, thus giving us a coefficient of variation of 85.15%. Lastly, the mean value for fiscal depth of the government is 4.69% while the standard deviation is reported to be 3.97%, resulting in a coefficient of variation amounting to 84.65%. It follows from the coefficient of variation that inflation in the economy exhibited a greater degree of variability compared to every other variable in the model. All the variables are also positively skewed as reflected in their coefficient of skewness being positive. They are also normally distributed, except for inflation, as their Jarque-Bera statistic are not significant at the 5% level.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Detecting the nature of the association without implying a cause-effect relationship can conveniently be executed using the correlation analysis, of which Table 3 captures our result.

Table 3: Result of the correlation test

	INF	MSS	IMP	GDP	GXGD
INF	1.0000				
MSS	0.2765	1.0000			
IMP	-0.4331	-0.3371	1.0000		
GDP	-0.2346	0.0499	-0.0711	1.0000	
GXGD	-0.4387	-0.3133	0.9045	-0.1174	1.0000

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

It is clear that a variable will correlate perfectly in a positive manner with itself and this explains the positive perfect correlation coefficient of 1.0000 in the Table 3. Apart from this, it is observed that the correlation concerning MSS and INF is weak but positive given the +0.2765 correlation coefficient between them. Here, inflation rises as money supply grows and decline as money supply decreases. Other variables on the contrary exhibits weak negative correlation with inflation. the correlation between import volume index (IMP) and inflation (INF) is fairly weak and negative given the correlation coefficient of -0.4331; while that of INF and GDP is negative and very weak given the correlation coefficient of -0.2346. The correlation concerning INF and fiscal depth of the government (GXGD) is negative and fairly weak as reflected with the -0.4387 correlation coefficient. The correlation concerning the explanatory variables raise no concern as none of the variables exhibited perfect linear correlation.

4.3 Test for Stationarity

Our analysis involves time series data which must be subjected to diagnostic test to detect their time series properties. This is done using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test for stationarity. Table 4 captures the result where the test is conducted based on the assumption of constant and trend.

Table 4: Stationarity test report

Variables	ADF Statistic I(0)	ADF Statistic I(1)	5% Critical Value	Order of Integration
INF	-3.3844	-6.5264**	-3.5950	I(1)
MSS	-4.1363**	-----	-3.5485	I(0)
IMP	-2.8446	-6.2615**	-3.5530	I(1)
GDP	-2.7379	-4.8873**	-3.5629	I(1)
GXGD	-2.1107	-6.2710**	-3.5530	I(1)

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

It is clear from Table 4 that only MSS is reported to be stationary at level, I(0), since its ADF statistic is more negative than the 5% critical value and statistically significant at the 5% level. every other variables only became stationary after they have been subjected to differencing at the first time, I(1). Thus, our variables are integrated in mixed order comprising of level and first difference. This points to us that using a conventional OLS approach will not yield the desired result. It is in this scenario that the use of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach becomes pertinent.

4.4 ARDL Result

The ARDL approach seems suitable for the identified order of integration among our variables and also aid in the estimation of both the short-run and long-run estimates of the model with ease. For the base model, Table 5 presents the original result based on the ARDL framework.

Table 5: ARDL regression result

Dependent Variable: INF		Selected Model: ARDL(1, 3, 1, 3, 1)		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
INF(-1)	0.5559	0.1349	4.1202	0.0006***
MSS	0.1728	0.1458	1.1845	0.2516
MSS(-1)	0.3430	0.1455	2.3582	0.0299**
MSS(-2)	0.4414	0.1935	2.2816	0.0349**
MSS(-3)	-0.1926	0.1461	-1.3185	0.2039
GDP	-3.3513	0.7817	-4.2871	0.0004***
GDP(-1)	1.3720	0.8170	1.6793	0.1104
GXGD	-6.6609	2.8025	-2.3768	0.0288**
GXGD(-1)	3.7914	3.4800	1.0895	0.2903
GXGD(-2)	1.3492	3.7677	0.3581	0.7244
GXGD(-3)	7.3307	3.5471	2.0667	0.0535
IMP	-0.0269	0.0537	-0.5001	0.6231
IMP(-1)	-0.0859	0.0554	-1.5512	0.1382
C	3.6407	8.9255	0.4079	0.6882
R-squared	0.8298		F-statistic	6.7507
Durbin-Watson stat	1.8730		Prob(F-statistic)	0.0002***

Note: ** and *** captures significance at 5% and 1% respectively.

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

The base model here helps us substantially to detect the role of expectation on the current value of inflation. Given the adaptive expectation ideology, the current rate of inflation (INF) depends on the previous rate of inflation (INF(-1)). Given our result, we observed that the previous year's inflation wielded a positive influence on the current rate of inflation, and such influence is reported to be statistically significant. As portrayed by the coefficient, the previous year's rate of inflation increased the current year's rate of inflation by 0.5559% on the average, pointing to the fact that if INF(-1) was high, then INF will also be high and the reverse holds. This finding aligns with Clark and Davig (2009) who observed that "expectations are vital drive in inflation dynamics, with long-run expectations,

which are indistinguishable to trend inflation, far essential than short-run expectations.”

The growth rate of broad money supply (MSS) is observed to wield a positive but inconsequential sway on the current rate of inflation. The one-year lag and two-years lag wielded a positive influence which is also statistically significant at the 5% level. It follows that the one-year lag of MSS increased INF by 0.3430% while the two-year lag increased INF by 0.4414%. These positive effect points to the fact that if last year’s MSS was high, inflation will be high and vice versa. It also points to the fact that it takes time for the growth in money supply to have effect on the price level in the economy. The third-year lag, however, is observed to wield a negative but insignificant weight on the current rate of inflation.

The growth in output is reported to wield a negative effect on the rate of inflation and such is also significant at the 1% level. This negative effect is adduced from the fact that as income grows, the growth in output will aid in curtailing demand-pull inflation which could have arisen as a result of rising aggregate demand emanating from the rise in income. Hence, a unit percent increase in GDP reduces INF by 3.3513% on the average. However, last year’s GDP, GDP(-1), wielded a positive but insignificant weight on the rate of current inflation.

The fiscal depth of the government (GXGD) portrays an interesting result where it put forth a reducing effect on the current rate of inflation, where such effect is also significant. This finding was earlier put forth by Atan and Effiong (2021) while trying to validate the reality of the ‘critical limit hypothesis’ (CLH) in Nigeria. As argued by the CLH, if government depth exceeds 25%, the resultant effect will be rising inflation. An exploration of our data over the study horizon revealed that the fiscal depth for Nigeria has not reached the 25% limit. Consequently, we could not expect it to cause a positive influence on the current rate of inflation. As the coefficient portrays, the current rate of inflation decreases by 6.6609% on the average if fiscal depth increases by 1% ceteris paribus. However, the lags in the GXGD, GXGD(-1) to GXGD(-3), all wielded a positive sway of INF though such effect were not significant.

The import volume index (IMP) with its one-period lag are shown to put forth a negative influence on the current rate of inflation, though their effects were statistically insignificant. The constant term which is not statistically significant portrays that the current rate of inflation will be 3.6407% if all the explanatory variables are held constant.

Our model is seen to be of good fit as the R-squared (0.8293) is high, showing that the independent variables explain about 82.93% of the overall changes in the current rate of inflation. The overall model is meaningful as the F-statistic is significant at 1%; and the model is free from serial correlation as the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.8730 is close to 2.0.

4.5 Cointegration Analysis

The reported order of integration of the time series variables was that MSS was stationary at level while other variables became stationary after first differencing. It will therefore be of utmost importance to test the existence of cointegration among the variables. Our analysis of this follows the ARDL F-Bounds test for levels relationship, where Table 6 captures the result.

Table 6: F-Bounds test result for cointegration

'null hypothesis': No levels relationship				
Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	3.9639***	10%	2.20	3.09
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		1%	3.29	4.37

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

It is clear from the F-Bounds test result in Table 6 that the F-statistic (3.9639) lies within the 1% I(0) bound statistic of 3.29 and that of the I(1) bound of 4.37. This portrays the significance of the test, calling for the 'null hypothesis' of "no levels relationship" to be overruled. Consequently, cointegration exist and we proceed to estimating the short-run dynamic error correction model and the long-run estimates.

4.6 ARDL Short-Run Error Correction Model

Given the manifestation of cointegration, Table 7 captures the result of our short-run error correction model (ECM) under the ARDL framework.

Table 7: ARDL short-run ECM result

Dependent Variable: D(INF)		Selected Model: ARDL(1, 3, 1, 3, 1)		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(MSS)	0.1728	0.1005	1.7196	0.1026
D(MSS(-1))	-0.2488	0.1506	-1.6518	0.1159
D(MSS(-2))	0.1926	0.1182	1.6298	0.1205

D(GDP)	-3.3513	0.6287	-5.3305	0.0000**
D(GXGD)	-6.6609	2.0775	-3.2062	0.0049**
D(GXGD(-1))	-8.6799	2.5717	-3.3752	0.0034**
D(GXGD(-2))	-7.3307	2.6782	-2.7372	0.0135**
D(IMP)	-0.0269	0.0403	-0.6662	0.5137
ECM(-1)	-0.4441	0.0806	-5.5127	0.0000***
R-squared	0.7387		Log likelihood	-108.4717
Adjusted R-squared	0.6477		Durbin-Watson stat	1.8730

Source: ResearcherComputation, 2022.

In the short-run, our result indicates that changes in MSS and its two-period lag wielded a positive influence on changes in inflation; while the one-period lag put forth a negative influence. In all cases, the variable put forth an insignificant effect on changes in the rate of inflation. such an insignificant short-run influence tally with the findings of Sultana et al. (2018) where they reported an insignificant inspiration of money supply on inflation within the economy of Bangladesh. Output growth is captured to be a driver of lower rate of inflation by wielding a negative effect, which is also significant at the 1% level. For every 1% increase in GDP, inflation decreases by 3.3513%. This portrays exigency of output growth in curtailing Nigeria’s inflation conundrum.

Variations in the fiscal depth of the government, D(GXGD), with its lags, D(GXGD(-1)) and D(GXGD(-2)), put forth negative effects on changes in the rate of inflation, with the effect being significant at the 5% level. A unit percent variation in fiscal depth of the government results in a 6.6609% decline in the variations in inflation; while the one-year lag and two-year lag of fiscal depth reduces variations in inflation by 8.6799% and 7.3307% respectively. Such negative effect aligns with the projection of the CLH that it is only when fiscal depth reaches 25% that inflation will begin to intensify. In our chosen period, none of the years reported fiscal depth of up to 25%, implying that the government can still increase its spending without intensifying the rate of inflation in the economy. Changes in import volume index is observed to wield a negative short-run effect on changes in inflation though such effect is inconsequential.

Our error correction mechanism which is expected to be negative and statistically significant adheres to the two conditions. From the coefficient, it is noted that about 44.41% of the short-run distortions in the model is corrected on a yearly basis before a long-run equilibrium is attained. The short-run model exhibits high degree of good fit as the R-squared portrays that the explanatory variables accounts for 73.87% of the total distortions in changes in the rate of inflation. With

the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.873 which is approximately 2.0, we are sure that our short-run regression model is free from serial correlation.

4.7 Long-Run Result

In the long-run, all the distortions experienced in the short-run are corrected. Our long-run result is presented in Table 8 where we observed the stable effect of the variables in influencing the rate of inflation.

Table 8: Long-run adjusted estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
MSS	1.7214	0.6927	2.4850	0.0230**
GDP	-4.4565	1.6198	-2.7513	0.0131**
GXGD	13.0827	7.5517	1.7324	0.1003
IMP	-0.2539	0.1485	-1.7098	0.1045
C	8.1974	18.8114	0.4358	0.6682
$EC = INF - (1.7214 * MSS - 4.4565 * GDP + 13.0827 * GXGD - 0.2539 * IMP + 8.1974)$				

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

As the long-run result in Table 8 portrays, the variables still behaves in a similar manner as it was in the short-run, except for fiscal depth of the government which now put forth a positive though an insignificant influence. The MSS still put forth a positive effect and the effect is now significant in the long-run at the 5% level of significance. This aligns with the earlier finding like Atan and Effiong (2021), Ofori et al. (2018), Sola and Peter (2013), Olalere (2019), and Ebipre and Amaegberi (2020). From the coefficient, a 1% rise in MSS will cause INF to increase by 1.7214% on the average. This positive effect proves the monetarists postulation that “inflation is a monetary phenomenon”. Amplification in money supply, consistent with the QTM, will lead to a rise in the price level at the full employment level of output. This forms the basis that the monetary authority needs to manage the magnitude of money supply in the economy to avoid incessant upswing in the price level. This role has been undertaken by the monetary policy committee (MPC) of the Central Bank of Nigeria through their adjustment of the monetary policy rate to suit the present economic situation.

Our long-run result further portrays that output growth is of great importance in fighting against inflation, as the variable wielded a negative and consequential influence on the rate of inflation. This result is in agreement with that of Ebipre

and Amaegberi (2020). A 1% rise in GDP reduces INF by 4.4565% on the average in the long-run. Boosting output growth aids in curbing demand-pull inflation that may arise from the increase in aggregate demand that may emanate from the rise in income. Import volume index is also observed to put forth a negative sway of the rate of inflation in Nigeria, though the effect is not substantial. Counter wise, fiscal depth of the government now put forth a positive effect on the rate of inflation. Though the effect is not significant, it points to the fact that over time, continuous government spending may exceed the 25% critical limit which will intensify inflation in the economy.

4.8 Post-Diagnostic Tests

Our post-diagnostic test centres on serial correlation test, heteroscedasticity test, normality test for residuals, and stability test. These tests aid in further determining the suitability of our parameter estimates for inferences.

4.8.1 Serial Correlation Test

The test for serial correlation aids in determining if the residual in one period is correlation with that of another period. The result is presented in Table 9 where the Breusch-Godfrey approach is being put to use.

Table 9: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test Result

F-statistic	1.667689	Prob. F(2,16)	0.2199
Obs*R-squared	5.520042	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0633

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

The F-statistic of 1.6677 having a probability of 0.2199 is clearly not significant at the 5% level. the ‘null hypothesis’ of no serial correlation is thus upheld and we conclude that the error terms are not prone to serial correlated.

4.8.2 Heterpskedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test is conducted to detect if our residuals carries a constant as required by one of the assumptions of OLS. Our test result is presented in Table 10 which is based on the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey approach.

Table 10: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test result

F-statistic	0.854856	Prob. F(13,18)	0.6066
Obs*R-squared	12.21511	Prob. Chi-Square(13)	0.5101
Scaled explained SS	3.506947	Prob. Chi-Square(13)	0.9954

Source: Researcher Computation, 2022.

As displayed in Table 10, the F-statistic (0.8549) having a probability of 0.6066 is not significant at the 5% level. It is clear from this angle that the ‘null hypothesis’ of no heteroscedasticity is upheld. It follows that the variance of our residuals are constant, that is, they are homoscedastic.

4.8.3 Normality Test for Residuals

It is required that the μ must be normally distributed in a regression equation. This calls for the normality test for residuals using the histogram approach where the Jarque-Bera (J-B) statistic is utilized. Figure 2 captures the test where the J-B statistic is 1.0894 and having a probability of 0.5800 which is not significant at the 5% level.

Figure 2: Histogram normality test for residuals

It follows from Figure 2 and the expressed statistics that the insignificance of the J-B statistic validates that the ‘null hypothesis’ of no serial correlation is accepted. Therefore, it can be stated categorically that the residuals were normally distributed, thus meeting the OLS assumption of normality of residuals.

4.8.4 Stability Test

The stability test aids in detecting the robustness of the parameter estimates for decision making. The cumulative sum of squares test is used in this regards, and Figure 3 portrays such.

Figure 3: Cumulative sum of squares test for stability

The test requires that the CUSUM of squares line needs to be within the 5% I(0) and I(1) bounds. Our Figure 3 clearly shows that his condition has been met. Categorically, the parameter estimates are stable and robust.

4.9 Granger Causality Test

The Granger causality test is conducted to ascertain the direction of flow of the relationship between money supply and inflation. Table 11 presents the findings of the test.

Table 11: Granger causality test result

'null hypothesis':	Observations	F-Statistic	Probability
INF does not Granger Cause MSS	34	0.43477	0.5145
MSS does not Granger Cause INF		5.84549	0.0217**

Note: ** captures significance at the 5% level.

Source: *Researcher Computation, 2022.*

As Table 11 clearly shows, the 'null hypothesis' that "INF does not Granger Cause MSS" is accepted since the F-statistic is not significant at the 5% level. Conversely, the "null hypothesis" that "MSS does not Granger Cause INF" is overruled since the F-statistic is significant at the 5% level. The rejection of the 'null hypothesis' implies that MSS causes INF – growth in money supply causes inflation. This causal behaviour is unidirectional as the causation only flows from growth in money supply to inflation.

5 Conclusion

The monetarist believes that “inflation is everywhere a monetary phenomenon” and stresses the role of monetary policy in curbing inflation in an economy. Households also forms expectations based on the past value of inflation, or along with anticipated government policies. In that way, their expectations could be either adaptive or rational. Still, the Critical Limit Hypothesis has clearly stated that if fiscal depth of the government exceeds 25%, the resultant effect will be inflation even under a condition of balanced budget. Consistent with this background, our study aimed at examining the influence of money supply on inflation in the midst of expectation and fiscal depth from 1986 to 2020. We utilized the ADF test to ascertain the stationarity of the time series variables; the F-Bounds test for checking on the existence of cointegration; and the ARDL method to estimate both the short-run and long-run estimates of the model.

From the unit root test, it was reported that our variables were integrated of order zero (level) and 1 (first difference). This led to the test for cointegration where the ARDL Bounds test revealed that cointegration exists. The ARDL result revealed that expectation plays a crucial role on the current rate of inflation since the past value of inflation wielded a positive effect which was also significant on the current rate of inflation. The implication is that if the past value of inflation was high, the current rate of inflation will as well be high and vice versa. From the ARDL short-run dynamic estimates, our result portrayed that changes in money along with its lags put forth an insignificant positive short-run effect on changes in the rate of inflation. Meanwhile, changes in output growth revealed to be a key variable that can reduce inflation as it put forth a negative and noteworthy effect on changes in inflation. As output grows, inflation tends to decline since the rise in output augment for the rise in aggregate demand which could have caused demand-pull inflation. Also, changes in fiscal depth of the government was observed not to be inflationary in nature as it wielded a negative and substantial sway on the changes in the rate of inflation. The reason behind such is that the fiscal depth of the government has not yet reached the 25% critical limit. Hence, increased government spending will not be inflationary within the stipulated limit. The import volume index was noted not to wield any substantial short-run influence on the changes in the rate of inflation; while the error correction mechanism portrayed that 44.41% of the short-run errors are corrected on yearly basis.

The long-run result portrayed the significance of money supply and output growth in curbing inflation. Consistent with the result, the effect of the growth in broad money was positive and significant, showing that rising money supply will put forth an intensified rate of inflation in the economy. This agrees to the QTM where changes in money supply only has its effect on the price level and not on the level of output. The effect of output growth on inflation was negative and such negative effect was also significant; pointing that if output increases, the level of inflation will decrease to portray the erosion of demand-pull inflation within the economy. Still in the long-run, fiscal depth now put forth a positive influence, though such was insignificant; while import volume index still exhibits a negative effect which is not also significant. To further strengthen our findings, the Granger causality test revealed that a one-way causality flows from growth in money supply to inflation, indicating that growth in money supply causes inflation. It follows from the findings that for inflation to be tackled successfully, there is need to maintain a stable level of money supply along with maintaining a substantial growth in output, while maintaining the fiscal depth within the 25% as suggested in the critical limit hypothesis.

References

- Amadeo, K., (2012). Obamacare Bill: A Summary of the Bill's 10 Titles. Retrieved from <https://useconomy.about.com/od/healthcarereform/a/Obamacare-Bill.htm>
- Atan, J. A. and Effiong, U. E. (2021). Fiscal Policy and Inflation in Nigeria: An Insight into the Critical Limit Hypothesis. *Quest Journal of Research in Business and Management (JRBM)*, 9(5), 66 – 73. <http://www.questjournals.org/jrbm/v9-i5.html>
- Bonatti, L., Fracasso, A. and Tamborini, R. (2022). What to Expect from Inflation Expectations: Theory, Empirics and Policy Issues. *Monetary Dialogue Papers, European Parliament*.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (2021). *CBN Statistical Bulletin*. CBN, Abuja.
- Christiano, L.J., and Fitzgerald, T.J., (2003), The Band Pass Filter. *International Economic Review*, 44, 435 – 465.
- Bernanke, B. S. (2007). Inflation Expectations and Inflation Forecasting. Speech at the Monetary Economics Workshop of the National Bureau of Economic Research Summer Institute, Cambridge, Massachusetts, July 10.
- Clark, T. E. and Davig, T. (2009). The Relationship Between Inflation and Inflation Expectations. Federal Reserve Bank of Kansas City. Authorized for public release by the FOMC Secretariat on 04/29/2016.
- Ebipre, P. and Amaegberi, M. A. (2020). Money Supply and Inflation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 8(3), 61 – 68.
- Egbulonu, K. G. and Wobilor, A. K. (2016). Impact of Fiscal Policy on Inflation in Nigerian Economy. *International Journal of Innovative Development & Policy Studies*, 4(3), 53 – 60.
- Friedman, M. (1989). *Quantity Theory of Money*. In *Money* (pp. 1-40). London: Palgrave Macmillan.

- Joshi, U. L. (2021). Effect of Money Supply on Inflation in Nepal: Empirical Evidence from ARDL Bounds Test. *International Research Journal of Makawanpur Multiple Campus (IRJMMC)*, 2(1), 84 – 98.
- Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money*. Springer.
- Moses, K. Tule, M. K., Obioma, E.C., Okpanachi, U.M., Odeniran, S.O. and Olaoye, O.J. (2015). Monetary Growth and Inflation Dynamics in Nigeria. *CBN Working Paper Series*, CBN/WPS/01/2015/02.
- Ofori, C. F., Danquah, B. A. and Zhang, X. (2017). The Impact of Money Supply on Inflation, A Case of Ghana. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR)*, 3(1), 2312 – 2318.
- Okon, J. I., Joshua, N. J., Arinze, N. P. and Effiong, U. E. (2021). Is the Inflation Problem in Nigeria Unsolvable? *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM)*, 9(11), 995 – 1008. <http://ijaresm.com/is-the-inflation-problem-in-nigeria-unsolvable>
- Olalere, S. S. (2019). The Impact of Money Supply on Inflation in Nigeria (1980 – 2009). *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 7(5), 31 – 36.
- Otto, G. and Ukpere, W. I. (2015). The Impact of Fiscal Policy on Inflation in Nigeria. *Risk Governance & Control: Financial Markets & Institutions*, 5(1), 123 – 132.
- Pigou, A. C. (1947). Economic Progress in a Stable Environment. *Economica*, 14, 180 – 188.
- Sabade, S. (2014). Is Money Supply the Cause of Inflation in India? An alternative postulate to Understand Inflation. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133 (2014), 379 – 382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.204>
- Sanusi, K. A. (2020). Fiscal Dominance and Inflation: Evidence from Nigerian and South African's Experiences. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 8(1), 1814508. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2020.1814508>

-
- Sola, O. and Peter, A. (2013). Money Supply and Inflation in Nigeria: Implications for National Development. *Modern Economy*, 4, 161 – 170.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/me.2013.43018>
- Sultana, N., Koli, R. and Firoj, M. (2018). Causal Relationship of Money Supply and Inflation: A Study of Bangladesh. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 9 (1) , 4 2 – 5 1 .
<https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2019.91.42.51>
- World Bank (2021). World Development Indicators. World Bank Group, Washington DC.